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Title: SOP for on-line sequential 2 step derivatization method creation using TriPlus RSH Sampling Workflow Editor

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Summary

The TriPlus™ RSH Sampling Workflow Editor is a program which allows to easily create and test methods for running the Thermo Scientific™ TriPlus™ RSH controlled by a Thermo Scientific™ Chromatography Data System (CDS).

Herein describes the automation parameters for a two stage methoximation / silylation derivatisation commonly applied for GC-MS based metabolomics sample preparation.

Procedure:

Sampling workflow editor (SWE) method

The steps for the sequential automated derivatization are edited in the TriPlusRSH sampling Workflow Editor Software version 1.4.0.4:

1. Open SWE software to create and edit methods for automated sample preparation

Different steps of the workflow are added by simple drag and drop of different steps

2. Add overlapping and select for step 1 and 2 overlap agitator and for step 3 inject GC as shown in figure 1

Figure 1 Add overlapping step: 1. click button add overlapping 2. A pop-up window will open and allow to select the overlapping steps

3. Select the tool used for first derivatization e.g. for our configuration liquid tool LS5 configured with syringe of 100 μL in the first **use tool** step

4. Insert a step for setting the temperature of the cooler drawer by drag and drop set temperature step

- Select module as: DrawerTempCtrl 1
- Set temperature at 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a tolerance of 0.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and wait for temperature set as False (setting to True will interrupt overlapping and lower the throughput monitored temperature did not get higher than 8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using over autosampler)

5. Set the temperature for first overlapping step related to first incubation:

- Select module as: agitator 1
- Set temperature at 55 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
- In the more options select a tolerance of 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and wait for temperature as true

6. Select agitator 1 in first **agitation vial** step and a speed of 300 rpm

- In more options default settings were selected as 5 s of on Time, 2 s of off Time and on state
- ⚠ Extra steps need to be added before **Transport vial overlap**

7. Add Clean Syringe: Toluene pre-methoximation wash of LS5 syringe

- Select wash source as large wash station 1
- Wash index 1 with 2 wash cycles and a volume of 70 μL
- For more options set the fill speed at 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ and wash source penetration depth 44 mm with a default dispense speed of 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$

8. Add Clean Syringe: Acetone pre-methoximation wash of LS5 syringe

- Select wash source as large wash station 2
- Wash index 1 with 1 wash cycles and a volume of 70 μL
- For more options set the fill speed at 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ and wash source penetration depth 44 mm with a default dispense speed of 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$

9. Rinse the syringe with MeOX reagent by adding **Get Volume** step:
- Set source Tray 4 (DrawerTempCtrl 1)
 - Source index: set the position MeOX aliquot
 - Set volume at 50 μL
 - Settings for more options are set as follow:
 - Use bottom sense: on
 - Height from bottom 1 mm
 - Filling strokes counts 0
 - Filling strokes volumes: 0 μL
 - Fill speed 2 $\mu\text{L/s}$
 - Dispense speed set as default: 100 $\mu\text{L/s}$
 - Front air gap set as default: 0 μL
 - Overfill rate: 0 %
 - Aspirate delay set as default: 1 s
 - Pressure compensation set as default: No
10. Add **Empty Syringe** step to dispense the reagent volume into waste
- Select waste port: Waste (large wash 1)
 - Dispense speed is default: 100 $\mu\text{L/s}$
11. Add **Get Volume** to pipette reagent used for methoximation
- Set source Tray 4 (DrawerTempCtrl 1)
 - Source index: use same position indicated above in step 7
 - Set volume at 50 μL
 - Settings for more options are set as follow:
 - Use bottom sense: on
 - Height from bottom 1 mm
 - Filling strokes counts 3
 - Filling strokes volumes: 10 μL
 - Fill speed 1 $\mu\text{L/s}$
 - Dispense speed set as default: 100 $\mu\text{L/s}$
 - Front air gap set as default: 0 μL
 - Overfill rate: 5 %
 - Aspirate delay set as default: 1 s
 - Pressure compensation set as default: No
12. Add Dispense Volume for methoximation of sample placed in cooled drawer
- Set destination: %samplerack% (Here the destination is the rack where the sample is placed it is indicated in the sequence within Xcalibur/Chromeleon)
 - Set Destination index: %sampleIndex% (Here the destination index is the position of the sample on rack it is indicated in the sequence within Xcalibur/Chromeleon)
 - Set volume: 50 μL
 - Settings for more options are set as follow:
 - Destination penetration depth: 7 mm
 - Dispense speed set as default: 100 $\mu\text{L/s}$
 - Pressure compensation set as default: no

13. In **Transport Vial Overlap** step set the destination of the sample for incubation in agitator as follow:
 - Set destination: %samplerack%
 - Set Destination index: %sampleIndex%
 - Set destination: Agitator 1
14. Set the incubation time: **Wait overlap**: 1200 s
15. The end of first incubation (first step of overlapping) is indicated by the pre-set step of overlapping: **Transport Vial Home Overlap**
16. The second overlapping step is defined by **USE tool**: the tool for silylation is selected e.g. for our configuration we kept the same tool used for methoximation LS5 equipped with 100 µL syringe
17. Set the temperature for second overlapping step related to second incubation: same settings as first incubation (step 5)
6. Select same agitation settings as step 6 for **agitation vial** step
 - ⚠ Extra steps need to be added before **Transport vial overlap** as for first overlapping step
17. Add **clean syringe**: pre-silylation wash syringe with Toluene
 - Select wash source as large wash 1
 - Wash index 1 (toluene) with 2 wash cycles and a volume of 70 µL
 - For more options set the fill speed at 5 µL/s and wash source penetration depth 44 mm with a default dispense speed of 100 µL/s
18. Add a second **Clean Syringe**: pre-silylation wash syringe with Acetone
 - Select wash source as large wash station 1
 - Wash index: 2 with 1 wash cycles and a volume of 70 µL
 - For more options set the fill speed at 5 µL/s and wash source penetration depth 44 mm with a default dispense speed of 100 µL/s
19. Rinse the syringe with reagent by adding **Get Volume** step:
 - Set source Tray4 (DrawerTempCtrl 1)
 - Source index: set the position of the MSTFA aliquot
 - Set volume as 50 µL
 - Settings for more options are the same as rinsing syringe LS5 with MeOX reagent in step 9
20. Add **Empty Syringe** step to dispense the reagent volume into waste
 - Select waste port: Waste (large wash 1)
 - Dispense speed is default: 100 µL/s
21. Add **Get Volume** to pipette reagent used for silylation
 - Set source Tray4 (DrawerTempCtrl 1)
 - Source index: same source index set in step 19
 - Set volume at 50 µL
 - Settings for more options are the same as settings for pipetting MeOX reagent in step 11
22. Add Dispense Volume for silylation of sample placed in cooled drawer

- Set destination: %samplerack%
 - Set Destination index: %sampleIndex%
 - Set volume: 50 μL
 - Settings for more options are set as follow:
 - Destination penetration depth: 7 mm
 - Dispense speed set as default: 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$
 - Pressure compensation set as default: no
23. In **Transport Vial Overlap** step set the destination of the sample for incubation in agitator as follow:
- Set destination: %samplerack%
 - Set Destination index: %sampleIndex%
 - Set destination: Agitator 1
24. Set the incubation time for silylation: **Wait overlap**: 900 s
25. The end of second incubation (second step of overlapping) is indicated by the pre-set step of overlapping: **Transport Vial Home Overlap**
26. Select the third tool in **Use Tool** step: LS3 equipped with 10 μL syringe for injection
27. Add **wait** step
- Time 120 s to cool the sample in cooled drawer prior injection
28. Add **clean syringe**: pre-injection wash syringe with nonane
- Select wash source as standard wash 1
 - Wash index 4 with 3 wash cycles and a volume of 7 μL
 - For more options set the fill speed at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ and wash source penetration depth 45 mm with a default dispense speed of 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$
29. Add **Get Liquid From Vial** step to pipette volume of sample from vial for injection
- Set source: %samplerack%
 - Source index: %sampleIndex%
 - Set volume at 1 μL
 - Settings for more options are set as follow:
 - Use bottom sense: on
 - Height from bottom 1.5 mm
 - Filling strokes counts 3
 - Filling strokes volumes: 2 μL
 - Fill speed 0.4 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$
 - Dispense speed: 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$
 - Front air gap set as default: 0 μL
 - Overfill rate: 10 %
 - Aspirate delay: 1 s
 - Pressure compensation set as default: No
30. Add **Wait For Sync Signal (GC)** step and Set the GC to GC1
31. In **Inject Sample GC Overlap** set injector as SSL, GC as GC1, analysis time to 690 s (if not sure can set to 0 and time will be estimated) and injection volume as 1 μL
- Settings for more options are set as follow:
 - Injection penetration depth: 45 mm
 - Injection penetration speed: 90 mm/s

- Injection speed: 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$
- Pre-injection delay: 0 s
- Post-injection delay: 0.1 s
- Injection signal mode set as default:
PlungerUp

32. Add **Clean Syringe** step: first post-injection syringe wash with nonane

- Select wash source as standard wash 1
- Wash index 1 with 1 wash cycles and a volume of 4 μL
- For more options set the fill speed at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ and wash source penetration depth 45 mm with a dispense speed of 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$

33. Add **Clean Syringe** step: second post-injection syringe wash with toluene

- Select wash source as standard wash 2
- Wash index 2 with 3 wash cycles and a volume of 4 μL
- For more options set the fill speed at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ and wash source penetration depth 45 mm with a dispense speed of 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$

34. Add **Clean Syringe** step: third post-injection syringe wash with acetone

- Select wash source as standard wash 3
- Wash index 3 with 3 wash cycles and a volume of 4 μL
- For more options set the fill speed at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ and wash source penetration depth 45 mm with a dispense speed of 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$

Annex 1

The modules installed on TriPlusRSH and used for 2-stage derivatization are shown in the figure below:

1. Tool Park station: X-axis extended rail with built in electronic and control
2. Autosampler's head with Z-axis
3. Agitator with controlled temperature for incubation with gentle shaking with 6 positions for 2 mL vials
4. Large wash station: containing 2x200 mL vials and a waste port
5. Cooler drawer for controlled cool temperature and sealed under nitrogen: 2x 54 positions tray
6. Standard wash station: 5x 10 mL vials

Annex 2

The settings of Autosampler's modules used for this method are listed below:

Note: Other modules can be added to the ATC also other modules are installed to the autosampler

LS3

- Location: Slot 1
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365D0311

LS5

- Location: Slot 2
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365H02141

Agitator 1

- Actual Temp: 55.0 °C
- Max Temperature: 200.0 °C
- Min Temperature: 30.0 °C
- Stdbby Temp control: on
- Stdbby Temperature: 55 °C

DrawerTempCtrl 1

- Drawer 1
- Actual Temp: 4.9 °C
- Max Temperature: 10.0 °C
- Min Temperature: 4.0 °C
- Stdbby Temp control: on
- Stdbby Temperature: 5.0 °C
- Temp Setpoint: 5.0 °C
- Close Current: 500 mA
- Close Speed: 70 %
- Drawer Sensors: Activated
- FanSpeed: 100 %
- Open Current: 400 mA
- Open Speed: 70%
- PeltierTemperature: -1.6 °C
- Strip Distance X: 25.0 mm

- Temp Offset: 0 d °C

Large Wash 1

- Pos 1 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 45.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 40.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 73.0 mm
 - > Height: 55.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 100SR
 - > Volume: 100.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 2 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 45.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 40.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 73.0 mm
 - > Height: 55.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 100SR
 - > Volume: 100.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Waste > Max Ndl Penetr Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 20.000 mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: Waste Vial
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

Standard Wash 1

- Pos 1 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR

- > Volume: 10.0 mL
- > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 2 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 3 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 4 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Waste > Max Ndl Penetr Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 20.000 mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: Waste Vial
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

SSL

- Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 35.000 mm
- Max Ndl Penetr Depth: 100.0 mm
- Min Ndl Penetr Depth: 18.0 mm
- Position Tolerance: 4.00 mm
- Z Tolerance: 20.0 mm

RobotArmLeft

- NdlGd motor 1 > Actual Position: 150 μ m
- Plunger motor 1 > Actual Position: 353 μ m
> Check Plunger :
- Tool control 1 > LS5 > Location: RobotArmLeft
> Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
> Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
> Length: 135.0 mm
> Syringe Type: SYT365F2141
> NdlGuide Coupling: 1078
> Plg. Coupling Count: 1078
> Tool Coupling Count: 1078
- X axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 150 μ m
> Total Axis Length: 1.207 m
- Y axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 0 μ m
- Z axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 0 μ m
- Acceleration rate: 30 %
- Default strategy: parallel
- DefaultWaste: none
- Homing Strategy: Default

ATC Station 1

- Slot 1 > LS5 > Location: Slot 1
> Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
> Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
> Length: 135.0 mm
> Syringe Type: SYT365H02141
> ParkSlotIndex: 1
> ToolPresent:
> Fiber Protection:
- Slot 2 > LS3 > Location: Slot 2
> Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
> Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
> Length: 135.0 mm
> Syringe Type: SYT365D0311
> ParkSlotIndex: 2
> ToolPresent:
> Fiber Protection:

- Slot 3 > ParkSlotIndex: 3
 - > ToolPresent:
 - > Fiber Protection:
- ToolEepromAccess:

Input Output 1

- Immediate > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
- OptoIn1 > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- PWMOut: > Signal On:
 - > OutputVoltage: 0 mV
- ResetButton: > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
- Simulated: > Signal On:
 - > Trigger Event: None
 - > Waiting Time: 60.0 s
- Software In > Signal On:
- Software Out: > Signal On:
- SWOut1 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- SWOut2: > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn1 > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn2 Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn3 Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut1 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut2 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut3 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- Beep Volume: 4

GC1

- Cryo Trap: None
- Fake Inj Delay: 15000 ms
- Injected: Start
- Prepare: None
- Ready: Gcready

GCRReady

- Signal On:
- BlockingTime: 0 ms
- Source: TTLIn1

Start

- Signal On:
- Destination: SWOut1
- DestinationAux: None
- PulseDuration: 300 ms